

GAN-based bone suppression using a combined loss function

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Accurate analysis of chest radiographs (X-rays) is essential for diagnosing diseases such as
4 pneumonia and lung cancer, yet bone structures often obscure critical soft tissues and lesions.
5 From an artificial intelligence perspective, bone suppression can be formulated using different
6 modeling paradigms that reflect distinct assumptions about the task. In this study, the problem
7 is addressed as a comparative methodological investigation, and three conceptually different
8 approaches are systematically evaluated within a unified experimental framework: denoising-
9 based regression using autoencoders, structured image-to-image transformation using U-Net
10 architectures, and distribution-based generative modeling using adversarial learning. In addition,
11 the impact of different loss configurations and training regimes on reconstruction quality is
12 examined. An enhanced generative adversarial network (GAN) with improved generator and
13 discriminator components and a combined loss function (Wasserstein, L1, perceptual, and
14 Sobel losses) is proposed to improve structural consistency and preserve soft-tissue appearance.
15 Model performance was assessed using the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and the multi-
16 scale structural similarity index measure (MS-SSIM). Among the evaluated approaches, the GAN
17 achieved the best performance, reaching a PSNR of 44.09 dB and an MS-SSIM of 0.9968, and
18 outperformed recently published methods evaluated on the same dataset. These results highlight
19 the importance of both modeling paradigm selection and loss formulation for achieving structurally
20 consistent bone suppression in chest radiographs.

21 **Keywords:** Generative Adversarial Network, Autoencoders, U-net, Bone Suppression, Chest Radiographs, X-ray Image Analysis,
22 Computer-Aided Diagnosis, Combined Loss Function

1 INTRODUCTION

23 Radiographs, commonly referred to as X-ray images, play an important role in medical diagnostics,
24 helping healthcare professionals identify various conditions and guide treatment plans. However, traditional
25 radiographs often present challenges due to the presence of bone structures, which can hinder accurate
26 diagnosis by casting shadows over parts of the lesion, leading to potential misinterpretations. Furthermore,
27 ionizing radiation poses a significant risk to the human body, especially with repeated exposure; therefore,
28 the current trend is to minimize this radiation as much as possible Hong et al. (2021). However, reducing
29 radiation doses decreases the quality of the resulting images, making diagnosis even more difficult
30 Uffmann and Schaefer-Prokop (2009). For this reason, computational image processing techniques for the

31 suppression of bones (ribs) from chest radiographs have become a part of assisted radiology Schalekamp
32 et al. (2013); Bae et al. (2022) and are an important preprocessing step in computer-aided diagnosis (CAD)
33 Horváth et al. (2013); Elgohary et al. (2022), contributing to the correct classification of lung disease
34 Han et al. (2022). This is mainly due to the use of convolutional neural networks, which have become a
35 phenomenon in recent years because they can offer high accuracy and robust performance. We proposed
36 a GAN-based method Arjovsky et al. (2017); Rani et al. (2022) to generate chest images with bones
37 removed and compared it with other neural network-based methods widely used in image processing,
38 namely autoencoders Bank et al. (2020); Vincent et al. (2008); Lee et al. (2018) and U-net Zhou et al.
39 (2020); Gusarev et al. (2017). To illustrate the potential impact of our method, we provide the following
40 example: Figure 1 presents an original chest radiograph, where bone structures obscure the visibility of
41 lung tissues. The application of our software, as demonstrated in the processed images, effectively removes
42 these bone structures, thereby enhancing the clarity of soft tissue details. This improved visualization
43 may facilitate more precise clinical interpretation of chest radiographs, potentially supporting diagnostic
44 assessment while remaining subject to further clinical validation.

Figure 1. Image a is original image from the X-ray, image b is output image with removed bones.

45 We conducted extensive experiments to evaluate the performance of our bone removal software using
46 various architectures and loss functions. The best results were achieved with the GAN neural network,
47 yielding a Multiscale Structural Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM) of **0.9968** and a Peak Signal-to-Noise
48 Ratio (PSNR) of **44.09 db**.

49 From an artificial intelligence perspective, bone suppression in chest radiographs can be formulated
50 using different modeling paradigms that reflect distinct assumptions about the task. In this study, we
51 address bone suppression as a comparative AI methodology problem and systematically evaluate three
52 conceptually different approaches: denoising-based regression using autoencoders, structured image-
53 to-image transformation using U-Net architectures, and distribution-based generative modeling using
54 adversarial learning. The aim is to provide a unified comparison of these paradigms under a consistent
55 experimental and evaluation framework in order to identify the most suitable modeling strategy for bone
56 suppression. As the differences between methods are often subtle and primarily structural, they are more
57 reliably captured by quantitative metrics than by direct visual inspection at standard resolution. Clinical

58 validation and reader-based studies are therefore considered subsequent research steps that follow the
59 establishment of a robust methodological foundation.

60 **Bones Removal Dataset**

61 In 1998, the Academic Committee of the Japanese Society of Radiological Technology (JSRT) launched
62 an initiative to establish the Standard Digital Image Database, a collection of chest radiographs containing
63 both normal cases and cases with lung nodules. This effort, undertaken in collaboration with the Japan
64 Radiological Society, was made possible through contributions of clinical cases from medical institutions in
65 both Japan and the United States. Over the years, the JSRT database has become a widely utilized resource
66 in medical imaging research, facilitating advancements in image processing, compression techniques,
67 display assessments, Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS), and the development of
68 machine learning-based computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems. The database comprises 247 digitized
69 chest radiographs (CXRs), including 154 cases with lung nodules – 100 classified as malignant, 54 as
70 benign, and 93 cases without nodules. These images were digitized using a laser scanner at a resolution of
71 2048×2048 pixels (0.175 mm per pixel) with a 12-bit grayscale depth. The images are stored in big-endian
72 raw format without headers Shiraishi et al. (2000). To expand the dataset, various augmentation techniques
73 were employed, including affine transformations such as rotation (-10 to 10 degrees), horizontal and vertical
74 translation (-5 to 5 pixels), horizontal flipping, and zooming. Additionally, image processing techniques
75 such as median filtering, maximum and minimum filtering, and unsharp masking were applied. As a result,
76 the dataset was expanded to 4081 image pairs at a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels, consisting of both
77 the original CXRs and their corresponding bone-suppressed versions Rajaraman et al. (2021). While this
78 augmentation strategy increases training diversity, it does not substitute for population-level variability
79 or independent institutional datasets. An example of these images is provided in Figure 2, where the
80 upper image displays a chest radiograph containing lung nodules, and the lower image presents the same
81 radiograph with suppressed bone structures.

Figure 2. Example of images from augmented JSRT dataset

2 METHODS

82 In this section, we present three deep learning strategies for bone suppression, each of which has been
83 custom-implemented to align with the architectures proposed in their foundational works. First, we designed
84 a custom autoencoder architecture inspired by the original model Gondara (2016), modifying certain layers
85 and hyperparameters to better suit our objective of bone suppression. Second, we developed a U-Net
86 Ronneberger et al. (2015) that closely follows the encoder-decoder structure described by Ronneberger
87 et al. but includes adjustments for improved handling of subtle bone features. Lastly, we constructed a
88 custom GAN model by combining key ideas from both the SFRM-GAN Rani et al. (2022) and Wasserstein
89 GAN Arjovsky et al. (2017) frameworks, ensuring that it could learn to suppress bones robustly without
90 sacrificing overall image fidelity.

91 2.1 Autoencoder

92 An autoencoder is a specific type of neural network that is primarily designed to encode input data
93 into a compressed representation and then reconstruct it to resemble the original as closely as possible.
94 Autoencoders are widely used in applications such as dimensionality reduction Meng et al. (2017); Wang
95 et al. (2014), classification Luo et al. (2017), anomaly detection Sakurada and Yairi (2014), and noise
96 reduction Chiang et al. (2019); Bengio et al. (2013); Creswell and Bharath (2019). For noise reduction,
97 denoising autoencoders are frequently employed. In these models, a noise layer is introduced immediately
98 after the input layer, followed by training the hidden and reconstruction layers with data that include noise.
99 A denoising autoencoder is an extension of a conventional autoencoder, in which the model learns to
100 map corrupted data to uncorrupted data by minimizing the loss function between their representations
101 Bank et al. (2020). The learning objective of this model is to recover the clean input from the noisy and
102 corrupted version. The corrupted signal, \tilde{X} , is generated from the clean signal, X , by random mapping
103 $\tilde{X} \sim q_D(\tilde{X}|X)$ Li et al. (2023).

104 In this work, a convolutional denoising autoencoder (CDAE) Gondara (2016) was used to address the
105 challenge posed by the ribs, which act as unwanted noise in chest radiographs. Unlike traditional fully
106 connected layers, the convolutional autoencoder employs convolution and pooling operations within the
107 convolutional neural network, effectively preserving two-dimensional spatial information Li et al. (2023).
108 It is well suited for images, as it preserves spatial locality by sharing weights across all input locations.
109 Gondara et al. have shown Gondara (2016) that CDA can be used for efficient denoising of medical images
110 by using small training datasets to achieve good performance. The ability of CDAEs to effectively denoise
111 medical images using a model trained on a relatively small training dataset has also been demonstrated
112 by Lee et al. (2018) on chest radiograph images. Kalish et al. Kalisz and Marczyk (2021) developed a
113 CDAE-based architecture and trained a model on the Bone Suppression dataset to remove bones from
114 chest radiographs (COVIDx dataset). Ahmed et al. Ahmed et al. (2021) employed a stacked convolutional
115 autoencoder (SCAE), an improved form of a basic denoising autoencoder with integrated convolutional
116 layers, to reduce noise in two-dimensional gel electrophoresis (2-DGE) images.

117 The input to the autoencoder consists of a $1024 \times 1024 \times 1$ image normalized to the range $[0, 1]$.

118 The convolutional autoencoder architecture in Figure 3 used for bone suppression operates on an encoder-
119 decoder framework. The encoder, composed of convolutional and cluster layers, extracts key features
120 while compressing the image into a compact representation, focusing on differentiating bones from other
121 structures. As the image moves through these layers, progressively abstract features are identified, from
122 basic edges to more complex structures like bone tissue.

Figure 3. Convolutional Autoencoder Architecture for Bone Suppression: The encoder-decoder framework begins with an encoder that uses convolutional (Conv2D) and pooling (MaxPooling2D) layers to extract and compress image features, focusing on distinguishing bones. Each layer progressively captures more abstract features. The decoder then reconstructs the image using upsampling layers (UpSampling2D), enhancing soft tissue visibility and reducing bone prominence. Here, f = number of filters and A = activation function either ReLU or Sigmoid.

123 The decoder then reconstructs the image in order to enhance the visibility of soft tissue while reducing
 124 bone prominence. By focusing on features related to soft tissues, the autoencoder effectively separates
 125 bone characteristics, producing a clearer image for diagnostic evaluation.

126 2.2 U-Net

127 U-net is an encoder-decoder model that is widely used in segmentation tasks, including the segmentation
 128 of chest radiographs Zheng et al. (2021); Osadebey et al. (2021); Novikov et al. (2018). Wang et al. Wang
 129 et al. (2020) proposed the multitask dense connection U-Net (MDU-Net) to address the challenge of
 130 bone segmentation from a chest radiograph. Their method combines the U-Net multiscale feature fusion
 131 approach, the DenseNet dense connection, and the multitasking mechanism to construct the proposed MDU-
 132 Net. For bone removal, Cardenas et al. Cardenas et al. (2021) used a U-Net architecture, demonstrating
 133 that bone removal from chest radiographs is feasible using a CNN combined with a patch-based approach
 134 by effectively segmenting and excluding bone structures. To succeed in the bone suppression task, we
 135 must input chest radiographs in which bone structures are prominent and must be distinguished from

136 other tissues. The U-net architecture can be effective in this context, with its unique up-sampling and
 137 down-sampling layers. In this case, we are using an original model from the paper U-Net: Convolutional
 138 Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation Ronneberger et al. (2015) together with various backbones
 139 of the Segmentation Model library Iakubovskii (2019). The input image to the U-net is $1024 \times 1024 \times 1$
 140 normalized in the range of $[0, 1]$. The proposed architectures can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The proposed U-Net architecture uses an encoder-decoder structure with skip connections. The encoder uses convolutional and pooling layers to capture progressively abstract image features, essential to distinguish bones from soft tissue. At the bottleneck, the image is compressed into a compact and detailed representation. The decoder then reconstructs the image with minimized bone features, using skip connections to retain fine-grained details. f = number of filters and A = activation function ReLU or Sigmoid.

141 At each layer of the encoder, the network applies filters to progressively extract image features, beginning
 142 with basic edge detection in the initial layers and advancing to more intricate patterns in the deeper layers.
 143 This hierarchical feature extraction is essential for distinguishing subtle differences between bones and
 144 surrounding tissues in radiographic images.

145 As the image passes through the encoder, its spatial resolution decreases while the extracted features
 146 become more abstract and informative. This trade-off allows the network to focus on the most relevant
 147 characteristics, particularly those necessary for identifying and suppressing bone structures. Upon reaching
 148 the bottleneck layer—the transitional point between the encoder and decoder—the image is transformed
 149 into a compact yet information-rich representation, emphasizing the critical features required for effective
 150 bone suppression.

151 The decoder then reconstructs the image using this refined information, ensuring that bone features are
 152 minimized while preserving other anatomical structures. The encoder's precise extraction of bone-related
 153 features plays a crucial role in this process, enabling the decoder to accurately suppress bones in the final

154 output. This systematic approach allows the network to accurately identify and modify bone structures
155 while maintaining the visibility of other essential anatomical details. The synergy between the encoder and
156 decoder in this process makes U-Net particularly effective for bone suppression in radiographic imaging,
157 demonstrating a sophisticated approach that goes beyond conventional segmentation to achieve targeted
158 image transformation.

159 **2.3 Feature Pyramid Networks**

160 In addition to the original U-Net architecture, we evaluated Feature Pyramid Networks (FPN) Lin et al.
161 (2017) within the same segmentation framework. FPN augments a backbone CNN with a top-down
162 pathway and lateral 1×1 convolutional connections to enable multi-scale feature aggregation. Instead of
163 constructing explicit image pyramids, FPN reuses intrinsic hierarchical representations of the backbone
164 (e.g., ResNet or EfficientNet), providing semantically strong feature maps at multiple resolutions with
165 moderate computational overhead.

166 In contrast to U-Net Ronneberger et al. (2015), which employs a symmetric encoder-decoder architecture
167 with full-resolution decoding and dense skip connections for pixel-level reconstruction, FPN performs
168 additive multi-scale fusion on backbone feature maps and applies task-specific prediction layers to
169 aggregated representations. Within the Segmentation Models library Iakubovskii (2019), FPN is adapted
170 for dense prediction; however, compared to U-Net, it emphasizes hierarchical semantic aggregation rather
171 than explicit spatial reconstruction, leading to different trade-offs between localization precision and
172 computational complexity.

173 **2.4 Generative Adversarial Networks**

174 Generative adversarial networks (GANs) consist of two components: the generator (G) and the
175 discriminator (D). Given a specific condition or input, the role of the generator is to produce realistic
176 images that ideally should be indistinguishable from the target images Creswell et al. (2018). Conversely,
177 the discriminator is responsible for distinguishing between the generated images and the actual target
178 images. In the context of bone suppression, the generator is expected to learn how to generate images in
179 which bones are effectively suppressed.

180 Rani et al. Rani et al. (2022) addressed the bone suppression task by modifying the architectures of
181 both the generator and discriminator in the Pix2Pix model. Their approach improved performance and
182 training stability by integrating the discriminator into the Wasserstein GAN framework, further enhanced
183 with a Gradient Penalty. Similarly, Han et al. Han et al. (2022) introduced a GAN-based disentanglement
184 learning framework, termed Rib Suppression GAN (RSGAN), to perform rib suppression by leveraging
185 anatomical knowledge embedded in unpaired CT images. Their method focuses on predicting the residual
186 map between the input chest X-ray (CXR) and its corresponding rib-suppressed version.

187 Our proposed architecture is inspired by the Wasserstein GAN Arjovsky et al. (2017) and the Spatial
188 Feature and Resolution Maximization GAN (SFRM-GAN) Rani et al. (2022). Due to the incorporation of
189 various loss functions and additional computational constraints, the input images are resized to $512 \times 512 \times 3$
190 and normalized to the range of $[-1, 1]$.

Figure 5. Bone Suppression GAN Architecture: The generator processes the input X-ray through convolutional and pooling layers to extract features, compresses them in a bottleneck layer, and reconstructs a bone-suppressed image via upsampling. The discriminator classifies the generated and real images, distinguishing between real and synthetic outputs.

191 Discriminator

192 The architecture of the discriminator, illustrated in Figure 6, progressively downsamples the input
 193 to determine whether an image is real or generated (real vs. fake); in our case, whether the image is
 194 suppressed or synthesized. To enhance training stability and accelerate convergence, batch normalization is
 195 applied after every convolutional layer except the first one. Each convolutional layer employs a stride of 2,
 196 effectively halving the spatial dimensions of the feature maps at each stage. This systematic reduction in size
 197 enables efficient downsampling of the input image while preserving essential features for discrimination.

198 Generator

199 The generator architecture in Figure 7 is modeled primarily after the U-net framework, which has
 200 demonstrated strong performance in bone suppression tasks, as evidenced by the results presented in
 201 Section 3.2. The architecture employs a series of convolutional blocks to progressively extract and encode
 202 complex features at multiple hierarchical levels, culminating in the bottleneck layer. Following this,
 203 transpose convolutions are applied to incrementally double the spatial dimensions of the feature maps.
 204 To maintain spatial consistency and preserve critical features that may be lost during downsampling, the
 205 upsampled outputs are concatenated with corresponding feature maps from the encoder path through skip
 206 connections.

207 During the GAN training process, the generator and discriminator networks are trained simultaneously.
 208 Automatic differentiation, implemented using gradient tape, plays a key role in updating the network

Figure 6. Discriminator architecture with down-sampling Conv2D layers, batch normalization, and a linear activation function. Filters and strides are noted for each layer. The f = a number of filters and A = activation function, which is, in this case, linear.

209 weights efficiently. The generator produces sample images, while the discriminator evaluates them,
 210 distinguishing between real and generated images. Both networks continuously adjust their weights based
 211 on the computed gradients, improving their performance through an iterative feedback loop. This ongoing
 212 refinement continues until the generator successfully produces images with effectively suppressed bone
 213 structures.

214 2.5 Loss Functions and Evaluation Metrics

215 We need some metrics to assess how well a model has performed; in our case, we have selected two
 216 evaluation metrics: the Structural Similarity Index Measure and the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio. Loss
 217 functions are either a combination of the evaluation metrics used as losses or completely different functions.
 218 These metrics provide quantitative ways to assess the effectiveness of bone suppression algorithms and are
 219 also used in other publications Lam et al. (2022), Kalisz and Marczyk (2021), Gusarev et al. (2017), Ren
 220 et al. (2021b), Rani et al. (2022).

Figure 7. Generator architecture with downsampling path (left) and an upsampling path (right) with skip connections between corresponding layers. Convolutional blocks progressively extract features, culminating in a bottleneck layer. Transpose convolutions in the upsampling path restore spatial resolution, while skip connections preserve fine details, enabling precise feature localization.

221 2.5.1 Evaluation metrics

222 It is essential to define suitable evaluation metrics to measure and compare the performance of the models.
 223 In this study, we will employ the same metrics used in previous research, namely the Multi-Scale Structural
 224 Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM) and the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR).

225 Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM)

226 The generated images are compared with the target images in terms of their structural similarity. A high
 227 MS-SSIM value indicates a more remarkable similarity in the structure of the target and the generated
 228 images Hore and Ziou (2010). MS-SSIM is a crucial metric for assessing image quality, extending beyond
 229 the traditional Structural Similarity Index Measure by incorporating multiple scales and structural features.
 230 It evaluates how well structural information is preserved between a reference image and a distorted
 231 version, offering a more comprehensive assessment of perceptual image quality. The Structural Similarity
 232 Index Measure equation consists of three components: i) luminance comparison function, defined as
 233 $l(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)}$, ii) contrast comparison function, defined as $c(x, y) = \frac{2\sigma_x\sigma_y + c_2}{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2}$, and iii) structure
 234 comparison function, defined as $s(x, y) = \frac{\sigma_{xy} + c_3}{\sigma_x\sigma_y + c_3}$, where x is the reference image (ground truth), y is the
 235 distorted image (predicted), μ_x, μ_y are the pixel sample means of x and y , σ_x^2, σ_y^2 are the variances of x
 236 and y , and σ_{xy} is the covariance of x and y ; c_1, c_2, c_3 are the variables to stabilize the division with a weak
 237 denominator. The SSIM is given as a weighted combination of these comparative measures, formulated as:

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = l(x, y)^\alpha \cdot c(x, y)^\beta \cdot s(x, y)^\gamma \quad (1)$$

238 where α, β , and γ are the weights of the appropriate comparison functions. By setting these weights to 1,
 239 the formula simplifies to:

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (2)$$

240 .
 241 After adding multiple scales and structural characteristics, the MS-SSIM is expressed as follows:

$$\text{MS-SSIM}(x, y) = [l_M(x, y)]^\alpha \cdot \prod_{j=1}^M [c_j(x, y)]^\beta \cdot [s_j(x, y)]^\gamma \quad (3)$$

242 where $l_M(x, y)$ is the luminance comparison function on the M-th scale (coarsest), $c_j(x, y)$ is the contrast
 243 comparison function on the j-th scale, $s_j(x, y)$ is the structure comparison function on the j-th scale, and M
 244 is the number of scales used for the calculation of MS-SSIM.

245 Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)

246 The PSNR quantifies the relationship between the highest possible signal strength, represented by the
 247 original image, and the noise level, which arises from differences between the original and processed
 248 images. This value is measured in decibels (dB). A higher PSNR indicates greater similarity between
 249 the original and processed images, signifying better image quality. In contrast, a lower PSNR suggests
 250 increased distortion or noise in the reconstructed image Hore and Ziou (2010).

251 The PSNR is expressed as follows:

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \times \log_{10} \frac{\text{MAX}^2}{\text{MSE}} \quad (4)$$

252 where MAX is the maximum possible pixel value of the image, and MSE is the result of the Mean Squared
 253 Error (MSE), a common metric for measuring the difference between actual and predicted values. It is
 254 calculated as $MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - p_i)^2$, where n is the number of observations in the dataset, y_i is the
 255 ground truth value, and p_i is the predicted value.

256 PSNR and MS-SSIM are used as the primary evaluation metrics, as they better reflect perceptual and
 257 structural image quality in bone suppression tasks. MSE is additionally reported in selected tables to enable
 258 direct comparison with previously published studies, where this metric is commonly provided, while MAE
 259 is not included due to its strong correlation with MSE and limited additional interpretative value in this
 260 reconstruction setting.

261 2.5.2 Loss functions

262 The Mean Squared Error (MSE), the Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM), and
 263 combinations of pixel-wise losses (MSE or MAE) with MS-SSIM are utilized as loss functions in selected
 264 models. The MS-SSIM metric is defined in Section 2.5, and the corresponding loss formulation is denoted
 265 as L_{MSSSIM} .

266 Pixel-wise losses quantify intensity differences between predicted and reference images. The Mean
 267 Squared Error (MSE), equivalent to the L_2 loss, penalizes larger deviations more strongly and is defined as

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - p_i)^2, \quad (5)$$

268 where n is the number of observations, y_i denotes the ground truth value, and p_i represents the predicted
 269 value. In contrast, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), corresponding to the L_1 loss, computes the mean
 270 absolute deviation,

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - p_i|, \quad (6)$$

271 and is less sensitive to outliers, which can help preserve fine structural details in lung regions.

272 To jointly enforce pixel-level fidelity and structural similarity, L_1 or L_2 is combined with L_{MSSSIM} in a
 273 Mixed Loss formulation introduced by Gusarev et al. Gusarev et al. (2017). The resulting loss functions
 274 are defined as

$$L_{\text{Mix}L_1} = \alpha \cdot L_{MSSSIM} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot L_1, \quad (7)$$

$$L_{\text{Mix}L_2} = \alpha \cdot L_{MSSSIM} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot L_2, \quad (8)$$

276 where α is a weighting hyperparameter controlling the balance between structural similarity and pixel-wise
 277 accuracy.

278 Each component of the composite loss addresses a different requirement of the bone suppression problem.
 279 Pixel-wise losses (L_1 or L_2) enforce intensity-level similarity between generated and reference images: L_1
 280 tends to better preserve fine soft-tissue textures, while L_2 promotes smoother global intensity transitions

281 that may reduce residual rib artifacts. The MS-SSIM term supports the preservation of multiscale structural
282 information in lung regions.

283 Within the GAN framework, additional components are used. The Perceptual Loss encourages similarity
284 in a high-level feature space to maintain a realistic soft-tissue appearance, while the Sobel Loss enforces
285 edge consistency, helping to attenuate high-frequency bone edges while preserving diagnostically relevant
286 anatomical boundaries. A full ablation analysis of all loss components would require training multiple
287 GAN variants and is therefore beyond the scope of this study; such an analysis is considered future work.

288 Although L_2 is convex and differentiable, making it suitable for stable optimization, it may lead to overly
289 smooth reconstructions. Therefore, L_1 is also evaluated, as it has been reported to better preserve contrast
290 and luminance details, often producing sharper outputs than L_2 Rani et al. (2022). Since the relative
291 effectiveness of L_1 and L_2 for bone suppression has not been conclusively established, both variants are
292 experimentally investigated in this study.

293 Loss Functions for the generator and the discriminator

294 The concept of Wasserstein Loss Arjovsky et al. (2017) is derived from the Wasserstein distance, also
295 known as the Earth-Mover's distance. It is calculated by taking the average of the critic's outputs for real
296 data and subtracting the average of its outputs for generated data. Here, the term "critic" refers to the
297 discriminator in the Wasserstein GAN framework, which estimates a continuous score rather than a binary
298 classification probability. The critic aims to maximize this difference by assigning higher scores to real data
299 and lower scores to generated data, whereas the generator strives to minimize this difference by producing
300 data that the critic perceives as real. The equation used to compute the Wasserstein Loss is as follows:

$$L_{\text{cGAN}}(G, D) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [D(X_i, Y'_i) - D(X_i, Y_i)] \quad (9)$$

301 where $L_{\text{cGAN}}(G, D)$ is the loss of the critic, G is the generator, and D is the critic; $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n$ is an average
302 for all n samples in the batch; $D(X_i, Y'_i)$ is the output of the critic for the real data pair, and $D(X_i, Y_i)$ is
303 the output of the critic for the generated data pair.

304 This loss function is consistently applied to the discriminator across all experiments and is also
305 incorporated into the generator's loss formulation. Four distinct loss functions derived from the Wasserstein
306 distance are evaluated. As the complexity of the loss function increases, a larger volume of training data is
307 required, as discussed in Section 3.3.

308 For the generator, the following loss functions are used and tested:

309 Wasserstein + L1/L2 loss

$$L_{\text{cGAN}}(G) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y'_i) + \delta [\alpha L_{L1/L2}] \quad (10)$$

310 Wasserstein + L1/L2 loss + Perceptual Loss

$$L_{\text{cGAN}}(G) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y'_i) + \delta [\alpha L_{L1/L2} + \beta L_{\text{Perceptual}}] \quad (11)$$

311 Wasserstein + L1/L2 loss + Perceptual Loss + Sobel Loss

$$L_{\text{cGAN}}(G) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y_i') + \delta [\alpha L_{L1/L2} + \beta L_{\text{Perceptual}} + \gamma L_{\text{Sobel}}] \quad (12)$$

312 where $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y_i')$ is the average score that the discriminator gives to the generated data across n
 313 samples, X_i is the conditioning input, and Y_i' is the generator-generated output; $\delta, \alpha, \beta, \gamma$ are the weight
 314 parameters for the additional loss components; $\alpha L_{L1/L2}$ is the result of the L_1 or L_2 multiplied by the
 315 weight parameter α . The loss formulations in Eqs. 10–12 can be interpreted as specific instances of a
 316 unified composite objective, where simpler variants are obtained by appropriately setting the weighting
 317 coefficients (e.g., $\beta = 0$ and/or $\gamma = 0$). $L_{\text{Perceptual}}$ is the loss function, also known as VGG-19 Loss, which
 318 employs the VGG-19 model pre-trained on ImageNet. This function enhances image synthesis quality by
 319 ensuring that the generated feature maps closely resemble those of the target image. It achieves this by
 320 measuring the Euclidean distance between the feature representations of the generated and target images,
 321 thereby improving information retention and reducing artifacts. The model can also be used with other deep
 322 learning architectures, such as ResNet50 and ResNet101, provided they are trained within the appropriate
 323 image domain Johnson et al. (2016). The result of $L_{\text{Perceptual}}$ is multiplied by the weight parameter β . L_{Sobel}
 324 is a loss function inspired by edge detection techniques. It calculates errors by comparing the gradient maps
 325 of the generated and target images in both the X and Y directions, effectively capturing discrepancies in
 326 image gradients Lu and Chen (2022). The result of L_{Sobel} is multiplied by the weight parameter γ . For all
 327 experiments, including all combinations of loss functions, the hyperparameters are defined as $\delta = 10000$,
 328 $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 10$, and $\gamma = 10$. The primary objective of the loss function, which integrates Wasserstein Loss,
 329 L_1/L_2 loss, Perceptual Loss, and Sobel Loss, is to capture both low- and high-frequency details within the
 330 image. This approach is intended to enhance detail preservation, ensuring that essential structures remain
 331 intact even after bone suppression.

3 RESULTS

332 For each training dataset size, multiple loss formulations were evaluated, and only the best-performing
 333 configuration, selected according to MS-SSIM and PSNR, is reported in Tables 1 and 5. The reported
 334 training times should therefore be interpreted as approximate indicators of relative computational demand
 335 rather than exact benchmarks.

336 The implementation was carried out using Python 3.6.8, TensorFlow 2.6.2, Segmentation Models v.1.0.1,
 337 and CUDA 11.4. The hardware setup included 20× Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6154 CPUs (@ 3.00 GHz), 2×
 338 NVIDIA TESLA V100 GPUs (32 GB), and 7.3 TB of RAM. The system operated on RedHat 6.0.11.

3.1 Results for Autoencoders

340 Since there are many experiments, showing only the best result according to the dataset size should help
 341 improve readability. Training of all models uses the Adam optimizer Kingma and Ba (2017), configured
 342 with a fixed learning rate of 0.001. Furthermore, a decay factor of 0.5 is employed with a patience parameter
 343 set to 5 in relation to the validation loss.

344 As shown in Table 1, the best-performing model was trained on 3,980 samples using the Mixed Loss
 345 with the L_1 loss function ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$), with a training duration of approximately 7.7 hours. The other models,
 346 which utilized the Mixed Loss with the L_2 loss function and the MS-SSIM loss function, demonstrated

Table 1. Best results for autoencoder experiments

Train/Test size	Loss function	Training time (s)	MS-SSIM	PSNR
400/100	$L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$	1 612	0.9805	31.332
1000/100	L_{MSSSIM}	3 853	0.9827	31.935
3980/100	$L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$	27 606	0.9847	32.850

347 slightly lower performance, suggesting that the number of training samples has only a minor impact on
348 overall effectiveness.

349 To further enhance performance, the feature extractor from a more complex pre-trained model was
350 integrated, replacing the encoder. Specifically, ResNet50 and EfficientNetB0 were used as backbone
351 architectures. All experiments in this setup were trained with the Mixed Loss using L_1 ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$) since the
352 best results without the pre-trained encoder were achieved with that loss function. Dataset comprised of
353 3,980 training samples and 100 test samples, as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Results for autoencoder experiments with pre-trained encoder

Backbone	Training time (s)	MS-SSIM	PSNR
ResNet50	20 989	0.9856	31.981
EfficientNetB0	38 989	0.9909	33.541

354 The findings of this experiment indicate that the use of a pre-trained encoder does not inherently lead
355 to a notable performance gain. While the usage of EfficientNetB0 backbone achieves better performance
356 compared to the previous autoencoder (AE) models, the improvement remains relatively modest.

357 3.2 Results for U-net and models from Segmentation Models library

358 For the U-Net experiments, the dataset size is limited to a maximum of 3,980 training samples and 100
359 test samples. This study evaluates the classic U-Net, as well as U-Net and FPN with various backbones
360 from the Segmentation Models library. The experimental setup uses a batch size of 4 and epochs set to
361 50. All models are trained using the Adam optimizer Kingma and Ba (2017) with a learning rate of 0.001.
362 Additionally, a decay factor of 0.5 is applied with patience set to 5, based on validation loss.

Table 3. Results for the experiments of U-net written from scratch

Loss function	Training time(s)	MS-SSIM	PSNR
L_1	54 348	0.9753	31.526
L_2	53 992	0.9756	31.396
L_{MSSSIM}	56 248	0.9908	33.389
$L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$	56 703	0.9939	37.075
$L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$	56 402	0.9915	33.877

363 Table 3 indicates that the Mixed Loss with L_1 is the most effective choice for this architecture. The U-Net
364 demonstrates a significant improvement over the autoencoder (AE), surpassing its best-performing models,
365 with a training duration of just over 15.8 hours.

366 The more advanced models from the Segmentation Models library significantly outperformed the previous
367 models, as shown in Table 4. The best-performing model utilized EfficientNetB0 as its backbone, which
368 also yielded the highest accuracy in evaluations beyond this study. Another advantage of this library is the

Table 4. Results for the experiments using Segmentation models library

Architecture	Loss function	Training time(s)	MS-SSIM	PSNR
U-net(EfficientNetB0)	$L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$	14 217	0.9962	38.590
U-net(EfficientNetB0)	$L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$	37 093	0.9955	38.536
FPN(ResNet50)	$L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$	45 671	0.9941	35.365
FPN(EfficientNetB0)	$L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$	61 050	0.9950	37.956
FPN(ResNet50)	$L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$	44 982	0.9946	36.174
FPN(EfficientNetB0)	$L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$	62 267	0.9947	36.343

369 reduced training time—training the best model required only approximately 4 hours. Among the tested
 370 loss functions, the Mixed Loss with L_2 ($L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$) achieved the best results; however, further experiments
 371 are necessary to determine the most effective loss function.

372 3.3 Results for Generative Adversarial Networks

373 A series of controlled experiments was conducted to determine suitable layer configurations and
 374 hyperparameters for the GAN model. For each dataset size, multiple settings were systematically evaluated,
 375 allowing us to analyze not only the best-performing models but also the impact of different loss formulations
 376 and training schedules on reconstruction quality. The key hyperparameters were selected empirically based
 377 on preliminary experiments and informed by prior work on GAN-based bone suppression, with the
 378 goal of ensuring stable convergence while preserving perceptual soft-tissue appearance and suppressing
 379 high-frequency bone edges.

380 All experiments used input images with a resolution of $512 \times 512 \times 3$, with a batch size of 4 for
 381 experiments using 3,980 training samples and a batch size of 8 for smaller datasets. The evaluated loss
 382 functions were: WL = Wasserstein Loss, WL_2 = Wasserstein Loss + L_2 , WL_1PS = Wasserstein Loss + L_1
 383 + Perceptual Loss + Sobel Loss, WL_2PS = Wasserstein Loss + L_2 + Perceptual Loss + Sobel Loss, and
 384 $WL_1PS(FT)$ denoting the fine-tuned variant of the combined objective.

Table 5. Results for the GAN experiments

Train/Test size	Loss function	Training time (s)	Epochs	MS-SSIM	PSNR
400/100	WL	206 615	2500	0.8893	24.357
400/100	WL_2	41 232	500	0.9876	35.619
1900/100	WL_2P	190 805	500	0.9926	39.790
1900/100	WL_1PS	193 345	500	0.9938	40.330
1900/100	WL_1PS	290 017	750	0.9938	40.535
1900/100	WL_2PS	193 435	500	0.9930	39.010
1900/100	WL_2PS	290 505	750	0.9930	39.011
1900/100	WL_2PS	328 840	850	0.9930	39.010
3980/100	WL_1PS	315 105	500	0.9967	43.314
3980/100	WL_1PS	468 202	750	0.9968	44.085
3980/100	$WL_1PS(FT)$	158 590	250	0.9820	33.625
3980/100	$WL_1PS(FT)$	313 590	500	0.9800	33.267

385 Table 5 provides a comprehensive overview of all evaluated GAN configurations across different dataset
 386 sizes, loss formulations, and training schedules. The results show a clear progression in reconstruction
 387 quality with increasing training data, highlighting the importance of dataset scale for stabilizing adversarial
 388 optimization and improving distribution-level alignment between generated and reference images.

389 For the smallest dataset (400 samples), the addition of the L_2 term to the Wasserstein objective
 390 substantially improves both MS-SSIM and PSNR compared to the pure adversarial loss, indicating
 391 that pixel-wise supervision is essential in low-data regimes. For medium and larger datasets, extending the
 392 objective with perceptual and gradient-based constraints (WL_1PS) consistently yields higher structural
 393 similarity and better suppression of residual bone edges compared to WL_2 or WL_2PS variants, which tend
 394 to produce slightly lower PSNR and MS-SSIM values despite longer training.

395 The best overall performance was achieved by the GAN trained on 3,980 samples using the combined
 396 Wasserstein + L_1 + Perceptual + Sobel loss for 750 epochs, reaching an MS-SSIM of 0.9968 and PSNR of
 397 44.085. Although this configuration required substantially longer training time (approximately 5.4 days),
 398 the results indicate that extended optimization with a composite loss promotes improved global structural
 399 consistency rather than merely minimizing localized pixel-wise errors.

400 The inferior performance of the fine-tuned variants further suggests that premature convergence or
 401 reduced training duration can negatively affect the balance between adversarial realism and structural
 402 fidelity. Overall, these findings are consistent with the observations of Rani et al. Rani et al. (2022),
 403 supporting the hypothesis that L_1 -based objectives combined with perceptual and gradient constraints
 404 provide a more suitable optimization landscape than L_2 -driven formulations for bone suppression tasks.

405 3.4 Comparative analysis between the models

406 Since the Autoencoder and U-Net models are trained at a resolution of $1024 \times 1024 \times 1$, while the
 407 Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) models operate at $512 \times 512 \times 3$, a direct comparison between
 408 these architectures may not provide meaningful insights. To address this, additional experiments were
 409 conducted in this section, where the best-performing AE and U-Net models were modified and retrained to
 410 match the $512 \times 512 \times 3$ resolution.

411 Training the GAN model at a higher resolution of $1024 \times 1024 \times 3$, which requires three channels, presents
 412 significant computational and time constraints. This section presents the results of these experiments and
 413 outlines the specific computational requirements for training the GAN model at this increased resolution.

414 A comparison of our findings with results from other studies in the field is provided at the end of this
 415 chapter. First, a direct comparison between the two models will be presented, followed by an experiment
 416 demonstrating how each model reconstructs an image from the test set, allowing for the calculation of
 417 MS-SSIM and PSNR metrics.

Table 6. Overview of the best models

Model	Training time	MS-SSIM	PSNR
AE + EfficientNetB0 (L_{MixL_1})	38 989	0.9909	33.541
U-net (Segmentation Models + L_{MixL_2})	14 217	0.9962	38.590
GAN (WL_1PS)	468 202	0.9968	44.085

418 Table 6 indicates that the GAN model delivers the best performance, with the only notable drawback
 419 being the extended training time of approximately 5.4 days. An interesting observation is that the MS-SSIM
 420 values remain relatively high across all approaches, suggesting that image reconstruction is effectively
 421 performed. However, PSNR plays a crucial role in determining the overall visual quality of the reconstructed
 422 images.

423 As shown in Figure 8, visual inspection reveals that all three methods achieve effective bone suppression
 424 with comparable global image appearances. Differences between reconstructions are subtle and not clearly
 425 distinguishable without quantitative analysis. The higher PSNR and MS-SSIM values obtained by the GAN
 426 therefore reflect measurable improvements in objective reconstruction consistency rather than visually
 427 dramatic differences. To further interpret these subtle differences, a localized region-wise analysis was
 428 performed after explicit spatial alignment of all reconstructions to the reference resolution.

Figure 8. Best results for direct comparison, where: (c) AE + EfficientNetB0, MS-SSIM: 0.9821 and PSNR: 36.07; (d) U-net from Segmentation models, MS-SSIM: 0.9963 and PSNR: 38.52; (e) GAN, MS-SSIM: 0.9985 and PSNR 45.61 (Output images resized to 512×512).

429 To further interpret the subtle differences observed in Figure 8, a representative case analysis was
 430 conducted after the explicit spatial alignment of all predictions to the reference resolution (Figure 9). A
 431 bone mask derived from the absolute difference between the original and reference bone-suppressed image
 432 ($|OR - GT|$) was used to separate bone and non-bone regions, and reconstruction errors were evaluated
 433 relative to the target image.

434 Within the masked bone region, U-Net achieved the lowest local mean absolute error ($MAE_{bone} =$
 435 0.0199), followed by AE (0.0206), while GAN exhibited slightly higher local deviation (0.0222). Outside
 436 the bone mask, residuals produced by the GAN were more uniformly distributed, indicating balanced

437 reconstruction across the entire image. Edge-based analysis revealed only minor differences among the
438 models within masked regions.

439 These findings highlight a fundamental optimization distinction. U-Net, trained predominantly with
440 L_1/L_2 -driven objectives, favors pixel-wise intensity agreement, leading to slightly lower localized absolute
441 error. In contrast, the GAN integrates adversarial and perceptual components that promote structural
442 coherence and distribution-level consistency. Consequently, although U-Net may minimize local absolute
443 deviation in specific regions, the GAN attains superior global PSNR and MS-SSIM values, reflecting
444 improved overall reconstruction balance rather than isolated pixel-level similarity.

Figure 9. Representative case analysis of region-wise reconstruction consistency after spatial alignment. Row 1 shows the original image (OR), the reference bone-suppressed ground truth (GT), and the predictions produced by U-Net, GAN, and AE. Row 2 presents the bone mask derived from $|OR - GT|$ together with the corresponding absolute reconstruction error maps. Row 3 visualizes the gradient magnitude of the target image and the edge error maps restricted to the bone mask. In this representative example, U-Net achieved the lowest local bone-region MAE (0.0227), while GAN exhibited a slightly higher local deviation (0.0264). However, the GAN demonstrated comparable edge-consistency behavior within masked regions and a more homogeneous distribution of residuals across the image. Despite the slightly higher local errors, GAN achieved the best global PSNR and MS-SSIM values, indicating improved overall structural consistency rather than strict minimization of localized pixel-wise deviations.

445 Within the masked bone regions, the U-Net achieved a slightly lower local absolute reconstruction error,
446 indicating closer pixel-wise intensity matching to the reference. In contrast, the GAN did not consistently
447 minimize local absolute deviation within these regions; however, it exhibited a more homogeneous
448 distribution of residuals across both bone and non-bone areas. This behavior suggests that the GAN
449 does not primarily optimize strict pixel-level similarity but rather promotes globally balanced structural
450 reconstruction.

451 From an optimization perspective, this behavior reflects the fundamental distinction between pixel-wise
452 reconstruction objectives and adversarial-perceptual formulations. The U-Net, trained predominantly with

453 pixel-wise reconstruction losses (e.g., L_1/L_2 loss), promotes strict intensity agreement at the local level,
 454 leading to slightly lower localized absolute error. In contrast, the GAN integrates adversarial and perceptual
 455 components that encourage structural coherence and distribution-level consistency across the entire image.
 456 Consequently, although U-Net may minimize local absolute deviation in specific regions, the GAN attains
 457 superior global PSNR and MS-SSIM values, reflecting improved overall reconstruction balance rather than
 458 isolated pixel-level similarity.

459 3.5 Comparative Analysis for 512×512 Input Size

460 To enable a direct comparison, the performance of models trained at the same resolution of 512×512
 461 will be evaluated. Following this, an experiment will be conducted to analyze the reconstructed images,
 462 highlighting differences in MS-SSIM and PSNR on a test sample.

463 The training parameters for the autoencoder and U-Net models were set to a batch size of 4 and 50 epochs.

Table 7. Direct comparison of the best models trained on images of size 512×512

Model	Training time	MS-SSIM	PSNR
AE ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$)	4 803	0.9837	31.703
U-net ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$)	14 067	0.9939	37.069
U-net (Segmentation Models + $L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	9 706	0.9955	37.592
GAN (WL₁PS)	468 202	0.9968	44.085

464 Table 7 shows that there is no significant difference in performance between models trained at 1024×1024
 465 and those trained at 512×512 . Once again, the GAN model achieved the best results, with consistently
 466 high MS-SSIM values across all cases. The most notable differences appear in PSNR, which can be visually
 467 examined alongside the original and target images.

Table 8. Direct comparison of the best-performing models trained on images of size 512×512 , evaluated on a single representative test image not included in the augmented JSRT dataset

Model	MS-SSIM	PSNR
c) AE ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$)	0.9804	33.602
d) U-net ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$)	0.9919	37.247
e) U-net (Segmentation Models + $L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	0.9957	40.014
f) GAN (WL₁PS)	0.9985	45.611

468 The results for the 512×512 models are summarized in Table 8. The reported metrics correspond to a
 469 single representative test image that was not included in the augmented JSRT dataset and are provided to
 470 illustrate the qualitative behavior of the best-performing configurations under identical spatial resolution.
 471 Across all evaluated paradigms, the GAN-based model achieved the highest MS-SSIM and PSNR values.
 472 Additionally, the FPN-based model exhibited unstable training behavior under the given experimental
 473 configuration, leading to the emergence of noticeable image artifacts in the reconstructed outputs. Since the
 474 FPN architecture was not part of the three primary modeling paradigms evaluated in this study (autoencoder,
 475 U-Net, and GAN), it was not analyzed further and is therefore not considered in the main comparative
 476 analysis.

4 DISCUSSION

477 In this study, three methodologies previously applied to this task were implemented and rigorously
478 evaluated: autoencoders (AE), U-Net, and generative adversarial networks (GAN). Each of these methods
479 operates on a distinct principle, making this study not only an assessment of their effectiveness but also
480 a comparison to determine the most suitable approach for this task. Autoencoders and U-Net, as non-
481 generative models, tend to be less susceptible to spurious noise introduced during training or inference.
482 However, the quality of the reconstructed images may sometimes be suboptimal, potentially complicating
483 the diagnosis based on the X-ray output. In contrast, generative adversarial networks, due to their inherently
484 generative nature, can exhibit greater sensitivity to such noise; yet, they outperformed the other approaches
485 overall based on quantitative metrics. Each architecture was systematically designed and evaluated across
486 a range of parameters, with the optimal configurations selected for the final assessment. It is essential to
487 emphasize that chest radiographs require interpretation by a qualified healthcare professional for accurate
488 clinical diagnosis.

489 One of the first methods to address the bone (rib) suppression challenge was the multiresolution
490 massive training artificial neural network (MTANN) Suzuki et al. (2006), which employed
491 decomposition/composition techniques and was trained on chest radiographs and dual energy bone images.
492 This method produced "bone-image-like" outputs, enabling the creation of "soft-tissue-image-like" images
493 with effectively suppressed ribs and clavicles. Despite such advancements, bone removal in radiological
494 imaging remains a significant challenge, as evidenced by numerous recent studies focusing on refining
495 existing methods, comparing them, optimizing workflows, and addressing limitations to improve usability
496 for radiologists and physicians. A major challenge in the bone suppression task is the scarcity of bone
497 suppressed data and the general lack of publicly available datasets, as reported Ren et al. (2021a); Schiller
498 et al. (2025). The state-of-the-art methods include deep learning architectures based mainly on autoencoders
499 (AE), U-net, and, more recently, generative adversarial networks.

500 Convolutional denoising autoencoders were chosen for this task because ribs can be treated as structured
501 interference rather than random noise. This learning paradigm enables the network to map input radiographs
502 containing bone structures to bone-suppressed target images by minimizing a reconstruction loss function.
503 This unsupervised machine learning technique was used because it learns to map corrupted data (bones) to
504 uncorrupted data (bone-suppressed images) by minimizing a loss function. This approach has previously
505 been used by Gusarev et al. (2017) and Kalisz et al. (2021). Our
506 results indicate that the best performance is achieved by the autoencoder with a pre-trained encoder (FPN
507 + EfficientNetB0) (Table 2). However, the performance improvement is not as significant as with the
508 autoencoder implemented from scratch (Table 1). In direct comparison to other methods, the autoencoder
509 achieved the worst results (Table 8). Compared to the implementation by Gusarev et al. (2017), our AE-based approach with a pre-trained encoder achieved a better MS-SSIM value (Table 9).

511 The U-Net Ronneberger et al. (2015) is a widely used neural network in medical imaging, mainly
512 designed for image segmentation Siddique et al. (2021). Due to its adaptability, various modifications and
513 integrations have been applied to bone suppression workflows in chest radiographs Li et al. (2020); Xu
514 et al. (2024); Schiller et al. (2025), making it a relevant choice for this study.

515 Schiller et al. (2025) developed xU-NetFullSharp, an advanced deep learning model for bone
516 suppression based on the U-NetSharp architecture, originally designed for medical image segmentation
517 Zunair and Hamza (2021). The xU-NetFullSharp improves performance by incorporating multi-scale skip
518 connections from shallow layer blocks to deeper layers, enhancing the model's ability to retain low-level

519 contextual information. They also implemented several U-Net-based architectures using TensorFlow and
 520 Keras, in combination with NumPy and OpenCV, including U-Net, Attention U-Net, U-Net++, Attention
 521 U-Net++, U-Net3+, U-NetSharp, and xU-NetFullSharp. Subsequently, these architectures were compared
 522 with the latest models for bone suppression, namely the autoencoder proposed by Kalisz and Marczyk
 523 (2021) and the ensemble model DeBoNet Rajaraman et al. (2022).

524 Our U-Net-based approach, which integrates Segmentation Models with a Mixed L_2 Loss function,
 525 outperformed xU-NetFullSharp in the reported evaluation metrics. Specifically, our model achieved an
 526 MS-SSIM of 0.996 and a PSNR of 38.59, while xU-NetFullSharp obtained an MS-SSIM of 0.986 and a
 527 PSNR of 33.81 (Table 9). Compared directly to the autoencoder, our U-Net-based architecture demonstrated
 528 superior MS-SSIM and PSNR values but was outperformed by the GAN, which achieved the highest results
 529 in both metrics (Table 8).

530 Oh and Yun Oh and Yun (2018) used a denoising approach based on conditional image-to-image
 531 translation with adversarial training within a GAN framework to model the conditional probability
 532 distribution of the output (bone-suppressed chest radiograph) given the input (original chest radiograph). In
 533 addition, Liang et al. Liang et al. (2020) demonstrated that GANs could effectively learn the nuances of
 534 bone suppression using adversarial learning techniques, resulting in images that preserve essential soft
 535 tissue details while minimizing bone artifacts. To improve image quality, GANs facilitate the generation of
 536 bone-suppressed images in a more automated and efficient manner. Techniques such as CycleGAN and
 537 conditional GAN have been employed to enhance the bone suppression process, allowing the simultaneous
 538 generation of bone-free images and organ segmentation Zhou et al. (2020); Eslami et al. (2020).

Table 9. Comparison of the models with other articles

Name	Model and technique	MS-SSIM	PSNR
[Gusarev et al. 2017]	Autoencoder and convolutional layers	0.907	-
[Eslami et al. 2020]	Conditional GAN and dilated convolutions	0.970	-
[Chen et al. 2019]	Cascade of multiscale CNN	0.977	39.40
[Zhou et al. 2018]	Multi-scale and conditional adversarial network	0.884	39.7
[Huang et al. 2020]	U-Net3+	0.985	33.69
[Kalisz et al. 2021]	Autoencoder and convolutional layers	0.982	32.60
[Rajaraman et al. 2021b]	Residual Network Model (ResNet-BS)	0.949	34.07
[Ziviani et al. 2022]	Conditional GAN	0.943	34.97
[Rani et al. 2022]	SFRM - GAN	0.989	42.83
[Zunair and Hamza, 2021]	U-NetSharp	0.985	33.72
[Schiller et al. 2024]	xU-NetFullSharp	0.986	33.81
<i>Our approach</i>	<i>AE + EfficientNetB0 (L_{MixL_1})</i>	<i>0.991</i>	<i>33.54</i>
<i>Our approach</i>	<i>U-net (Segmentation Models + L_{MixL_2})</i>	<i>0.996</i>	<i>38.59</i>
Our approach	WL₁PS)	0.997	44.09

539 In 2020, Zhou et al. Zhou et al. (2020) incorporated enforced semantic features into a dilated conditional
 540 GAN, which allows for a better contextual understanding of the images being processed. This integration
 541 not only improves the quality of the generated images but also aligns the output more closely with clinical
 542 expectations. Their model was trained by enforcing the pixel-wise intensity similarity and the semantic-
 543 level visual similarity between the generated radiograph and the ground truth by optimizing an L_1 loss of
 544 the pixel intensity values on the generator side and a feature matching loss on the discriminator side. Since
 545 a naïve combination of adversarial loss and pixel-wise L_1 loss failed to capture the semantic information of
 546 radiographs, a feature matching loss was introduced on top of the discriminator. This approach allowed the
 547 discriminator to extract feature representations from each pair of real and generated images using activations

548 from its fourth convolutional block and to compute the mean of the element-wise L_1 distance between
549 them. the resulting loss function for optimizing the discriminator was defined as $D^* = \mathcal{L}_{adv_D} + \lambda_{fm}\mathcal{L}_{fm}$,
550 where L_{adv_D} is the adversarial loss of the discriminator, L_{fm} is the feature matching loss, and λ_{fm} is a
551 constant to adjust the weight of the feature matching loss. The utilization of feature matching loss enforced
552 the similarity of high-level feature maps.

553 Our GAN architecture, enhanced by the incorporation of Wasserstein Loss along with L_1 loss, Perceptual
554 Loss, and Sobel Loss functions, delivered the best performance. Its metrics, including a PSNR of 44.09
555 dB and an MS-SSIM of 0.9968, confirm the model's ability to suppress bone structures effectively while
556 preserving high image quality and critical soft tissue details. Compared to other studies Ziviani et al. (2022);
557 Rani et al. (2022); Eslami et al. (2020) evaluated on the same dataset, our method achieved the highest
558 reported MS-SSIM (0.997) and PSNR (44.09) values under the reported experimental settings.

559 Despite achieving the best quantitative performance in our experiments, the GAN-based model is
560 associated with a higher computational cost compared to the autoencoder and U-Net architectures. This
561 reflects the inherent complexity of adversarial learning and the composite loss formulation, representing
562 a methodological trade-off rather than an implementation limitation. In practical deployments, training
563 time could be reduced through multi-GPU parallelization, mixed-precision training, or resolution-aware
564 strategies, facilitating scalable application in larger datasets or clinical workflows.

565 This study is limited to evaluation on the publicly available JSRT dataset and its augmented variants.
566 Although augmentation increases training variability, it does not introduce patient-level diversity or
567 independent acquisition conditions. The findings should therefore be interpreted as methodological
568 benchmark results rather than evidence of clinical generalizability, and validation on independent multi-
569 center datasets and external test sets remains necessary to assess robustness under heterogeneous real-world
570 acquisition conditions.

5 CONCLUSION

571 The increased visibility of the lung regions in bone-suppressed images can aid in the inspection of soft-tissue
572 structures and may support downstream computer-aided analysis, while dedicated clinical validation is
573 required to assess the diagnostic impact. This suggests that the proposed GAN configuration may represent
574 a promising methodological direction for medical imaging preprocessing.

575 The presented GAN optimization integrates a combined objective composed of Wasserstein loss together
576 with pixel-wise, perceptual, and gradient-based components (L_1 , Perceptual loss, and Sobel loss), aiming
577 to balance intensity fidelity, structural consistency, edge preservation, and distribution-level realism in the
578 generated outputs. This study was designed as a methodological evaluation of modeling strategies rather
579 than a clinical validation study.

580 In addition to the GAN-based approach, we also trained models for bone removal using autoencoders
581 and a custom implementation of the U-Net architecture from scratch. However, their performance across
582 the evaluated metrics was consistently lower compared to the proposed GAN model, highlighting the
583 advantage of integrating multiple loss components in this context.

584 The source code and trained models developed in this work are publicly available to the research
585 community on GitHub, promoting transparency, reproducibility, and further development in this important
586 area.

587 Future studies could explore its integration into clinical workflows, where collaboration with radiologists
588 can provide critical insights into its practical impact on diagnosis. In addition, future advances, including
589 optimized training strategies, refined loss functions, and adaptation to other imaging modalities that demand
590 high detail denoising and feature preservation, could further enhance the utility of this approach. The
591 findings of this research provide a methodological reference point for the further development of bone
592 suppression models within computer-aided imaging workflows.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

593 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
594 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

595 **Lukáš Jochymek:** Methodology, Software, Writing - Original draft, Data Curation, Visualization. **Markéta**
596 **Vašínková:** Writing - original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Vít Doleží:** Conceptualization,
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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

602 The datasets analyzed in this study are publicly available through the Japanese Society of Radiological
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CODE AVAILABILITY

604 The source code used in this study is publicly available at: [https://github.com/lowoncuties/](https://github.com/lowoncuties/Bone-suppression-in-X-Ray-medical-images-of-lungs)
605 `Bone-suppression-in-X-Ray-medical-images-of-lungs`.

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